

Scaling Up Equitable Access to Community-Based COVID-19 Testing: Strategies from the RADx-UP Initiative

Executive Summary

The COVID-19 pandemic has magnified how structural racism and other structural determinants of health affect the lived experience of the public health emergency on marginalized and minoritized communities. These communities include Black, Latino or Latinx, American Indian, Alaska Native, Asian, and Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islanders communities as well as people who are incarcerated, low-income, or disabled, in addition to older adults, children, LGBTQIA, and birthing people. Achieving an equitable response to COVID-19 and future public health emergencies requires: reducing barriers that preclude populations from reaching health services in a timely manner, centering equity in policy making decisions, and engaging communities. Community-based COVID-19 testing can ensure all populations have access to testing, which is a key step to linking people to treatment and reducing disparities in COVID-19 health outcomes.

Insights from the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Initiative offers a timely perspective into strategies for supporting community-based testing to respond to COVID-19 surges and variants. In this policy paper, we propose a policy framework to identify common barriers to equitable

COVID-19 testing and facilitate the scaling-up of the solutions that emerged to address them. We identify five key policy levers and three foundational components that are necessary to lead to measurable improvements in health equity. We aim for health leaders—including policymakers, community organizers, and other health care practitioners—to use these community-engaged policy strategies to inform community-based testing for future COVID-19 surges and variants.

Policy Levers

Equitable **access** requires removing barriers that prevent people from reaching COVID-19 testing sites

Efficient, transparent, and equitable **resource allocation** is needed to meet the needs of populations experiencing higher risk, vulnerability, or exclusion

Accurate and reliable **data** are crucial to support decision-makers to address health disparities and implement mitigation measures during the COVID-19 pandemic

Trustworthy, clear, and culturally responsive **communication and messaging** is needed to connect patients, providers, and communities to resources

Payment reforms that create incentives for quality of care and support innovative care management can accelerate efforts to advance health equity

Foundational Components

Community engagement promotes health equity, demonstrates the trustworthiness of health organizations in communities, and centers marginalized and minoritized voices

Cross-sector partnerships spanning health systems and communities they serve often have greater impact than efforts of any one stakeholder group acting alone

Regulatory guidance that seek to streamline processes, protect health data, and reduce administrative burden are important to support work within each policy lever

KEY STRATEGIES FOR COMMUNITY-BASED COVID-19 TESTING

We identified five key strategies for community-based COVID-19 testing based on real-world experiences from RADx-UP awardees and an environmental scan of the literature:

- *Extending the reach of existing health care infrastructure to expand access* includes creating additional sites, including walk-up testing sites, mobile testing sites, or at-home solutions, as well as funding community health workers (CHWs)
- *Using novel tools and measures to bolster equitable distribution and resource allocation* to identify communities burdened by high social and economic deprivation or comprising predominantly marginalized and/or minoritized populations
- *Increasing data protections and community feedback when standardizing data collection to address health inequities* includes deidentifying data, developing culturally

sensitive common data elements (CDEs), and engaging communities in data collection

- *Creating transparent, community-informed communication and messaging* includes collaborating with trusted community leaders and supporting community input to build trust, allay concerns, and ensure messaging is culturally and linguistically responsive
- *Developing provider payments that facilitate community-based delivery of testing beyond a traditional clinical setting and reduce cost sharing for populations seeking testing* are key facilitators to increase testing uptake

LOOKING AHEAD: CONSIDERATIONS FOR POLICYMAKERS, PROVIDERS, AND RADx-UP PROJECTS

Community-based models that have promoted COVID-19 testing can be adapted more broadly to ensure individuals have access to health care resources that they trust and understand. Case examples in the policy paper illustrate the needed shift to support and finance community-based strategies, which have the greatest potential to sustainably reduce health disparities and bridge health equity gaps. Key steps policymakers, providers, and RADx-UP projects can take are:

- Develop accessible health services and public health interventions that overcome systemic inequities
- Allocate resources and services that address context-specific community barriers by using data tools and developing partnerships and networks
- Implement and operationalize data strategies that identify racial and ethnic disparities, embed community engagement, and support technical capacity
- Design communication and messaging strategies that reflect the community context and culture, use bidirectional channels, and embed cultural humility
- Advance payment reforms that support community-based care delivery models and remove systemic barriers to health services

Key Takeaways: Strategies to Embed Equity in COVID-19 Testing Efforts

For Policymakers:

- Extend health coverage to redress systemic inequities in insurance rates; support the development of equity-focused metrics; and support policies to extend services beyond traditional health care settings
- Encourage cross-sector data sharing to improve quality and timeliness of data application; and build on experience using disadvantage indices to identify geographic areas or populations exhibiting the greatest need for resources and COVID-19 testing
- Generate policies and funding mechanisms to modernize data management systems; support technical capacity for data de-identification and anonymization to help ensure compliance with privacy regulations (e.g., HIPAA) through data-sharing networks
- Support development of community advisory boards and consult community-partnership experts to encourage bidirectional communication; and support platforms and coalitions to embed community perspectives in communication strategies
- Create incentives to advance private and public payment models that include community health workers (CHWs)

For Providers:

- Expand walk-in/no appointment options; provide vaccination and testing beyond business hours; and partner with community-based organizations (CBOs) to organize events that are tailored to the cultural and linguistic needs of specific communities
- Collaborate with local health departments and CBOs to integrate real-time population-level data and identify communities experiencing vulnerability

- Use real-time, disaggregated data to understand gaps in service delivery and identify context-specific interventions
- Employ bilingual and bicultural staff to deliver care that is culturally and linguistically responsive; engage with local leaders to disseminate information; and respond to health concerns with empathy and cultural humility to build community connection and trust
- Support alternative payment models that embed health equity and support community-based care delivery models

For RADx-UP Projects:

- Deliver testing through community-centered delivery models (e.g., mobile testing and vaccine units, community-based primary care sites)
- Use disadvantage indices to generate data to address community-level health disparities; and partner with community health centers to identify communities experiencing higher risk for COVID-19 exposure and adverse outcomes
- Develop data visualizations to uncover trends and disseminate findings to inform decision making related to policies or specific tactics to increase COVID-19 testing; support alignment of data with community goals, including co-development of measures, data collection, and reporting plans
- Generate evidence on the most effective communication strategies to reach different communities; and test messaging with communities for key decisions and policies
- Use NIH funding to support CHW salaries and provide supports to help CHWs find sustainable career opportunities